

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D5.1 – “Report on project identity and website”

Work Package 5 - Dissemination and Exploitation

Task 5.1 - Communication activities

Due date of deliverable: 30 April 2022

Actual submission date: 29 April 2022

Project Acronym	StoRIES
Call	H2020-LC-GD-2020
Grant Agreement No.	101036910
Project Start Date	01-11-2021
Project End Date	31-10-2025
Duration	48 months

INFORMATION

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Status	Draft 1.0 / Draft 2.0 / Final	29-04-2022

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

CO	Confidential	
CL	Classified	
PU	Public	X

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

StoRIES is an EU-funded project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101036910.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
WG(s)	Working Group(s)
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is a report on the project identity and website of the StoRIES project. It focuses on activities carried out to define documents and communication tools within the consortium and their dissemination to third parties as well as the European Commission. In addition, the structure of the website of StoRIES project is presented here.

StoRIES project is funded under the call H2020-LC-GD-2020 and aims to set up a research ecosystem to develop energy storage technologies in Europe.

The first part of the document details the visual identity of StoRIES, including the project logo, dissemination materials, and document templates. The project visual identity, via its colours and shapes, aims to allow for an easier identification of the project by the public, thus ensuring better visibility. It also maintains coherence among the partners during their interaction with the public through communication and dissemination activities.

The second part focuses on the StoRIES website, which will support the project's visual identity and has the aim of functioning as a reference for any person interested in learning about the project and the progress of its activities. It portrays the project's proposal, outlining its goals, instruments, the roles of each partner and timeline of work.

This deliverable will be closely linked to D5.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan. As part of this plan the StoRIES website will act as the focal point of online dissemination and communication activity for the project, while additional social media channels (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook) will amplify the key messages from the project website. It will reach many different target audiences, including industrial networks and associations, Academia and research, public stakeholders at EU, national and local level, other related national and EU-funded projects, media, and the wider public in and beyond Europe.

INTRODUCTION

Purpose of the document

The StoRIES project is born with the idea of addressing this challenge, bringing together a consortium of beneficiaries like facilities from the European Strategy Forum on Research Facilities (ESFRI), technology institutes, universities, and industrial partners to jointly improve the economic performance of energy storage technologies. The main technological objectives of StoRIES are linked to the energy storage development by providing access to world-class research infrastructures and services, with a focus on improving materials for devices and optimizing hybrid energy systems with a view to make energy technologies more competitive and reducing costs. In addition, StoRIES focuses on the analysis of socio-technical and environmental aspects of new developments and systems and provides training and education on these issues.

This document falls under the Work Package (WP) 5 Dissemination and Exploitation and will report on the identity of the StoRIES project and the website. The main objective of this deliverable is to provide the necessary material and support the efficient realisation of the dissemination and communication activities planned during the project’s lifetime.

Relation to other project deliverables

The deliverable is produced under WP5 Communication and Exploitation, that aims to establish an appropriate and effective communication strategy of the project to relevant stakeholders, the large community of energy industry and academia in general and to pave the way towards the exploitation of the StoRIES results. In this way, this deliverable establishes the StoRIES project visual identity and delivers the appropriate tools to support the dissemination and communication activities through conferences, newsletters, and publications. These tools include a project visual identity expressed in the form of a logo, document templates and a website, and that will be used throughout the lifetime of the project by all the project deliverables, not only WP5, to allow for a better identification of the project.

This deliverable will be closing linked to D5.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan, due in month 9 of the project.

1 PROJECT IDENTITY

1.1 Logo

The logo of StoRIES has the goal of representing the project in every communication material and activity. The logo consists firstly of a mention to the project's acronym, underlining the letters "RIES", representing "Research Infrastructure Eco-System". Secondly, the logo contains on the left six hexagons representing different energy storage technologies, referring to the attention the project gives to hybrid energy storage. The colour codes of the project are apple-lime green and turquoise blue, typically associated with energy transition.

Figure 1: Logo of StoRIES

1.2 List of communication and dissemination materials

The communication and dissemination materials where the logo and project identity will be used are the following (non-exhaustive list):

- Project website
- Social media
- All documents developed within the framework of the project and in particular the documents to be submitted to the European Commission such as deliverables, agendas, minutes of meetings, etc.
- PowerPoint presentations used for communication and dissemination activities carried out by consortium partners
- Dissemination materials such as leaflets, presentation template, brochures, roll-ups, etc.
- Physical and online events organised or participated in by the project.

1.3 Templates

All the documents developed within the framework of the project and supporting partners' work are subject to a specific format template. The following templates have been developed to be used during the project's lifetime:

- Text template (Word)

- Minutes of meeting template (Word)
- Presentation template (Power Point)
- Deliverable template (Word).

Figure 2: Presentation template

Figure 3: Presentation template

Figure 4: Text template

Figure 5: Deliverable template

Figure 6: Deliverable template

Name of Meeting
Location, 09 Month 202_

MINUTES OF MEETING

NAME OF MEETING

Location, Date

ATTENDANCE LIST

Day 1

Discussion	Name	Signature

- Text
- Text

Decision:

- Text
- Text
- Text

Decision:

- Text
- Text
- Text

Decision:

Table 1: Example of Table

Title	Title	Title	Title

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101036910

1

Figure 7: Minutes of meeting template

2 PROJECT WEBSITE

2.1 Structure

The project website of StoRIES was planned by project partner CLERENS, in collaboration with the coordinating team of the project from KIT. Initial meetings were held between the two partners to decide on a website map that could convey all the information needed about the project and fulfil other needs. Lift Design, a company specialized in visual identity and website design, was in charge of building and implementing the website on the platform Wix; the text and structure was drafted by CLERENS and the graphics were developed by Lift Design.

2.1.1 Introduction

The StoRIES website aims to reach any person interested in acquiring more knowledge on the project. The website seeks to provide information on the project, the aim and objectives, instruments, the roles of each partner and the foreseen timeline of work.

The website will be regularly updated with the progress of the work made in the project, publicising and promoting future events, such as TNA calls, workshops, summer schools and news items on the development of its activities. The website will be managed by CLERENS, who will oversee updating it as needed and collecting inputs and suggestions from partners concerning news and other content to be published on the website.

2.1.2 Domain

The domain of the StoRIES website will be <https://www.storiesproject.eu>, allowing also for the purchase of a related e-mail address, info@storiesproject.eu. The website is hosted on the platform Wix, which has a hosting plan included. The web hosting stores the files of the website and make them accessible for visitors worldwide.

2.1.3 Graphic Identity

The StoRIES website has been designed on Wix environment using the available design tools of the platform. Wix is a dynamic website editing platform that allows to implement several graphic features such as background animations. The identity makes use of the colour palette of the logo, focusing on shades of blue and green and other related undertones.

2.2 Content

Below, figure 8 shows a map of the website, with all content pages, both parent and child one.

Figure 8: Map of the StoRIES website

2.2.1 Homepage

The homepage of the website is a scroll-down page with a series of content previews, divided into the following sections: description of the goals, upcoming events, latest news and contact form. All previews are linked to their main page of reference.

Figure 9: StoRIES website homepage

The header contains a menu that leads to the other sections of the website, while on the footer, the project disclaimer and linked social media handles are present.

Figure 10: StoRIES website homepage presentation of the project

Upcoming Events

Figure 11: StoRIES website homepage latest "upcoming events"

Figure 12: StoRIES website homepage "Latest news"

Figure 13: StoRIES website homepage "Contact" form

Figure 14: StoRIES website header

Figure 15: StoRIES website footer

2.2.2 About

The "About" section will provide general information on the project, such as its vision, concept, its objectives, the structure of the Consortium and a timeline of activities that will be implemented in the project's lifetime. It also contains a section dedicated to the partners involved in the Consortium.

2.2.2.1 Why StoRIES?

The overview under "Why Stories?" underlines the main vision and overall goal of the project, as well as the instruments and procedure that will be implemented to experiment and demonstrate the ideas brought by the project.

2.2.2.2 Hybrid Energy Storage

This page gives an introduction on hybrid energy storage. Over the time, latest updates and news will be published in this section to provide more information on the topic.

Hybrid Energy Storage

Hybrid Energy Storage Technologies provide the opportunity to combine complementary characteristics and to overcome barriers and drawbacks of single technologies alone. The European targets to increase the renewable energy penetration in the energy system (e.g. Fit for 55 and REpower EU) implies a key role for energy storage enabling a range of services providing performance and sustainability at the same time. Rather a combination of various energy storage technologies (electrochemical, chemical, thermal, mechanical and electrical storage) is needed in order to provide the expected performance regarding energy system capacity and duration offering the desired flexibility. Moreover, the more renewables will penetrate the market, the greater the need of flexibility in energy storage applications in face of changing market conditions.

Combining a high-energy storage technology with high-power technology is one of the common approaches as, for example, the combination of Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES) or supercapacitors with batteries would offer, or electricity storage with conversion in chemicals (P2X) for long-term, large scale energy storage. Such combinations shall also ensure an optimal use of materials for storage technologies thus contributing to increase the sustainability of the energy system as a whole.

Figure 16: StoRIES website "Hybrid Energy Storage"

2.2.2.3 Partners

The "Partners" page showcases the list of partners involved in StoRIES, as well as a short description of their organisation and role within the project. The logo is also clickable, with a link leading to the organisation's website.

Figure 17: StoRIES website "Partners" page

2.2.2.4 Structure

The "Structure" page showcases the management structure of the project, including the advisory board, the selection panel and extended network in the form of tables.

Figure 18: StoRIES website "Structure" page

2.2.2.5 Strategy

The "Strategy" page showcases the specific activities that will be undertaken to reach the main vision of StoRIES, as well as the specific targets to reach. It also provides an overview of a timeline, underlining which main activities will take place in which moment of the project's lifetime.

2.2.2.6 Working Groups

The "Working Groups" page provides an overview of the activities that will be carried by the four Working Groups (WGs) within the framework of the project.

Figure 19: StoRIES website "Working Groups" page

2.2.3 Access

The "Access" section showcases the ES research infrastructures open to users from the StoRIES consortium and beyond, including the procedure for applications.

2.2.3.1 Research Infrastructures

The "Research Infrastructures" provides a list of the infrastructures, including a detailed description of their facility and their location with the help of a map.

Figure 20: StoRIES website "Research Infrastructure" page

2.2.3.2 Calls

The "Calls" section gives information on the topic of the periodical transnational access calls for access to the infrastructures.

2.2.3.3 Procedures & Rules

The "Procedures & Rules" section defines the procedures for access providers, applicants, and users.

2.2.3.4 FAQ

The "FAQ" deals with a list of specific frequently asked questions from potential applicants.

2.2.4 Downloads

The "Downloads" section contains all the publicly available project materials that will be produced and will be uploaded on the website, available for download to the public. The types of materials include communication materials, scientific publications and public deliverables and reports.

Figure 19: StoRIES website "Downloads" page

2.2.4.1 Communication Materials

The "Communication Materials" section provides an overview of all communication materials used for the project. It is also possible to request specific communication materials for specific events attended by partners. All resources will be downloadable by the users.

2.2.4.2 Scientific Publications

In this section, the scientific publications in the framework of the project will be made available.

2.2.4.3 Deliverables and Reports

The "Deliverables and Reports" section includes all the latest reports for StoRIES project and all public deliverables of the project.

2.2.5 Events

The "Events" section provides an overview of upcoming events, either open for public or just limited to the Consortium, such as General Assembly meetings to which the general public cannot participate, but can read about its outcomes nevertheless.

2.2.6 News

The "News" section list all the latest news regarding the project and partners.

2.2.7 Forum

The "Forum" section offers a collaborative area to the users of the website. After signing up, the members can begin a conversation thread, as well as add texts, pictures, videos, and open debates. To maintain a safe environment for the website readers and members, the comments and posts share will be monitored by moderators from CLERENS.

2.2.8 Newsletter popup

The newsletter popup appears when the user arrives on the website. This gives the user the opportunity to subscribe to the newsletter to receive the biannual newsletter.

Figure 21: StoRIES website "Contact" page

2.3 Privacy and Cookie Policy

The [Privacy and Cookie Policy](#) of the StoRIES website ensures that personal data of users is processed according to the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

(See <http://clerens.eu/privacy-cookie-policy/>)

2.4 Website statistics

The StoRIES website statistics will be monitored through the Google Analytics platform, which allows to keep track of the website performance and plan a reactive communication strategy. Personal data of users will be processed according to GDPR.

Google Analytics is a popular platform for website analytics which allows to analyse various data aspects of website performance. Results from the platform will be available and shared with the Consortium at all meetings to assist the discussions on strategies on how to increase project's outreach.

3 SUPPORT ROADMAP OF LC-GD-9-1-2020

StoRIES is funded under the Call LC-GD-9-1-2020, which focuses on European Research Infrastructures capacities and services to address European Green Deal

The corporate identity of StoRIES, which comprises its visuals, style, and website, mirrors the concepts of the call. The content production within the website and its social media handles will focus on the topics touched by the call and support the activities implemented.

StoRIES will therefore also be available to establish links and synergies with the other projects funded under this call (e.g., PAUL (Pilot Application in Urban Landscapes - towards integrated city observatories for greenhouse gases) and RI URBANS Research Infrastructures Services Reinforcing Air Quality Monitoring Capacities in European Urban & Industrial Area) as well as other projects. During the project there will be continuous monitoring to seek for additional ones if/when necessary.

CONCLUSION

The corporate identify of StoRIES will be present throughout the project’s lifetime, as it will be implemented in all content and communication material produced. The identity of the project shall be respected by partners using the templates drafted by the project’s Communication team and by respecting the visual rules set in them. Partners are invited to contact CLERENS in case of any doubt concerning the project identity, as well as to notify CLERENS of any issues that may arise from it.

The StoRIES website will act as a strong tool to communication and disseminate project information and outcomes, and any other information relevant from project perspective. The progress of the project activities and updates from Consortium partners will gradually be implemented to the website. The website and related statistics will comply with data protection policy. Throughout the project lifetime, the usability of the website will be reviewed or observed to bring further improvements.

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